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Investigating the influence of infrastructure on Sustainable Development Education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of infrastructure on sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. The study was motivated by the growing concern over inadequate educational infrastructure and its implications for effective teaching and learning of sustainable development concepts in secondary schools. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population comprised principals, vice principals, teachers, and senior secondary school students in selected Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. A sample size of 300 respondents was selected using multistage sampling techniques, while 286 questionnaires were properly completed and returned for analysis. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Infrastructure and Sustainable Development Education Questionnaire (ISDEQ). The instrument was validated by experts and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, while linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that infrastructure significantly influences sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. The study further showed that adequate classrooms, ICT facilities, laboratories, libraries, electricity supply, and conducive learning environments positively enhance students' academic performance, environmental awareness, innovation, and sustainability learning outcomes. The regression result indicated a positive and significant relationship between infrastructure and sustainable development education ($\beta = 0.683$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that infrastructural development remains a critical factor in promoting quality education and achieving sustainable development goals in Nigeria. The study recommended increased government investment in educational infrastructure, provision of modern ICT facilities, regular maintenance of school facilities, and integration of sustainability-oriented infrastructure in Federal Unity Colleges.

Keywords: Infrastructure, Sustainable Development Education, Federal Unity Colleges, Educational Facilities, ICT Infrastructure and Quality Education

INTRODUCTION

Education is widely recognized as a critical instrument for achieving sustainable development because it equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes required to address social, economic, and environmental challenges (Gabdo et al., 2025). The adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals

(SDGs), particularly Goal 4, which emphasizes inclusive and equitable quality education, has intensified global attention on the quality of educational infrastructure and learning environments in schools (Ahmad & Magaji, 2024). In developing countries such as Nigeria, the effectiveness of sustainable development education largely depends on the availability and adequacy of educational infrastructure, including classrooms, laboratories, libraries, digital facilities, water supply, electricity, sanitation systems, and instructional technologies (Gabdo & Magaji, 2025). According to Hassan, Groot, and Volante (2025), infrastructure significantly influences the quality of teaching and learning outcomes within educational institutions.

Infrastructure remains a fundamental pillar in the realization of sustainable development because it supports human capital development, innovation, environmental awareness, and social inclusion (Okon et al., 2025). Sustainable educational infrastructure not only provides physical learning spaces but also creates an enabling environment that promotes creativity, critical thinking, technological adaptation, and environmental responsibility among learners (Bello et al., 2025). Fadipe (2025) observed that inadequate infrastructure in Nigerian educational institutions continues to hinder effective curriculum implementation and quality learning experiences. The challenge is particularly significant in secondary schools where overcrowded classrooms, poor laboratory facilities, insufficient digital technologies, irregular electricity supply, and deteriorating buildings negatively affect teaching and learning processes.

Federal Unity Colleges, popularly known as Unity Schools, were established by the Federal Government of Nigeria to promote national integration, educational excellence, and equal educational opportunities across the country. These colleges are expected to serve as models of quality education and national cohesion. Over the years, however, concerns have emerged regarding the state of infrastructure in many of these schools. Despite increased government expenditure on education and infrastructural interventions, many Federal Unity Colleges still face infrastructural deficits that undermine the effective delivery of sustainable development education. Fadipe (2025) revealed that infrastructure for curriculum implementation in Unity Colleges was perceived as inadequate by stakeholders, thereby affecting the quality of science education and sustainable learning outcomes.

The relationship between educational infrastructure and sustainable development education is multidimensional. Adequate infrastructure enhances access to quality learning, facilitates practical and experiential teaching methods, and improves students' understanding of sustainability-related concepts such as environmental conservation, climate change, renewable energy, and responsible citizenship. Conversely, poor infrastructure contributes to low student motivation, weak teacher performance, and reduced educational effectiveness (Musa et al., 2022; Yunusa et al., 2024)). According to Ezeudu and Fadeyi (2024), infrastructural deficiencies such as inadequate laboratories, limited ICT facilities, poor sanitation systems, and unstable electricity supply continue to widen educational inequalities and weaken efforts toward achieving sustainable educational goals in Nigeria.

Furthermore, the growing importance of technology-driven education in the twenty-first century has increased the demand for modern educational infrastructure. Digital learning facilities, internet connectivity, and smart classroom technologies have become essential for integrating sustainable development principles into contemporary educational systems (Magaji & Adelabu, 2012). UNESCO (2023) emphasized that ICT infrastructure contributes significantly to educational sustainability by enhancing innovation, research capacity, and knowledge dissemination. However, many Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria still struggle with inadequate digital infrastructure, thereby limiting students' exposure to global sustainability knowledge and technological competencies.

The issue of infrastructure in Nigerian schools has also attracted policy attention because of its implications for educational quality and national development. The Federal Government of Nigeria has introduced several educational reforms and intervention programmes aimed at improving school infrastructure and learning environments. Nevertheless, challenges relating to poor funding, weak maintenance culture, corruption, population growth, and uneven resource distribution continue to affect infrastructure provision in schools (Enaberue et al., 2024). Hassan et al. (2025) argued that improved

educational investment and infrastructural support are associated with better learning outcomes and institutional efficiency in Unity Schools.

In addition, sustainable development education requires learning environments that encourage environmental responsibility and social participation. Educational facilities such as eco-friendly classrooms, functional laboratories, waste management systems, renewable energy facilities, and water conservation structures are increasingly considered important components of sustainability-oriented schools. Ojo (2022) maintained that infrastructure development should be integrated with sustainability objectives in order to promote long-term educational and societal transformation. This perspective is particularly relevant for Federal Unity Colleges because of their strategic role in shaping future leaders and promoting national unity.

Despite the significance of infrastructure in advancing sustainable development education, empirical studies focusing specifically on Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria remain limited. Most existing studies have concentrated on general educational infrastructure, higher education institutions, or basic education without adequately examining how infrastructural conditions influence sustainable development education within Unity Colleges. This creates a knowledge gap that necessitates further investigation. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the influence of infrastructure on sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. The study aims to assess the extent to which infrastructural facilities contribute to effective teaching and learning of sustainable development concepts, students' academic performance, environmental awareness, and overall educational quality in Unity Schools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Concept of Infrastructure

Infrastructure refers to the fundamental physical and organizational facilities required for the effective functioning of institutions and societies (Abdulazeez *et al.*, 2022). In the educational sector, infrastructure encompasses classrooms, libraries, laboratories, information and communication technology (ICT) facilities, electricity supply, water systems, sanitation facilities, furniture, administrative buildings, and recreational facilities that support teaching and learning processes. According to Owoye and Yara (2011), school infrastructure constitutes the physical resources that facilitate effective educational delivery and students' academic performance. Similarly, Ajayi and Yusuf (2009) described educational infrastructure as the collection of physical facilities and learning resources that create a conducive environment for educational activities.

Educational infrastructure is critical because it directly influences the quality of instruction, students' motivation, teachers' effectiveness, and overall institutional productivity. Adequate infrastructure enhances students' participation in learning activities, encourages practical knowledge acquisition, and promotes innovation and creativity. Conversely, inadequate infrastructure often leads to overcrowded classrooms, poor concentration, reduced academic achievement, and low teacher morale. In the context of Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria, infrastructure plays an essential role in achieving educational excellence and supporting sustainable development education.

Modern educational infrastructure has expanded beyond traditional classroom buildings to include digital technologies, internet connectivity, renewable energy facilities, environmental sanitation systems, and smart learning tools. UNESCO (2023) emphasized that sustainable educational systems require technologically equipped and environmentally friendly infrastructures that support twenty-first-century learning and sustainability education. Therefore, infrastructure is not merely a physical requirement but a strategic investment in human capital development and sustainable societal transformation.

Concept of Sustainable Development Education

Sustainable development education refers to the process of equipping learners with the knowledge, values, attitudes, and skills necessary to promote sustainable economic growth, environmental protection,

and social equity for present and future generations. The concept emerged from the broader philosophy of sustainable development popularized by the Brundtland Commission Report of 1987, which defined sustainable development as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

According to UNESCO (2020), education for sustainable development enables individuals to make informed decisions and take responsible actions for environmental integrity, economic viability, and social justice. Sustainable development education integrates critical issues such as climate change, environmental conservation, poverty reduction, gender equality, peace building, renewable energy, and responsible consumption into teaching and learning activities. It promotes critical thinking, problem-solving skills, participatory learning, and civic responsibility among students.

In Nigeria, sustainable development education has become increasingly important because of growing environmental challenges, insecurity, poverty, unemployment, urbanization, and climate-related disasters. Federal Unity Colleges, as strategic secondary educational institutions, are expected to integrate sustainability principles into their curriculum and learning environment. However, achieving this objective depends significantly on the availability of adequate infrastructure that supports practical learning, technological innovation, and environmental awareness.

Federal Unity Colleges and Educational Development in Nigeria

Federal Unity Colleges, commonly referred to as Unity Schools, were established by the Federal Government of Nigeria after independence to foster national unity, integration, and educational excellence among students from diverse ethnic, religious, and cultural backgrounds. These colleges were designed to provide equal educational opportunities and promote national cohesion through quality secondary education. According to Fafunwa (1974), Unity Schools were established as instruments for national integration and educational standardization across Nigeria.

Over the years, Federal Unity Colleges have contributed significantly to human capital development and national educational advancement. The schools are recognized for their relatively structured administrative system, qualified teaching personnel, and federal government support. Nevertheless, many Unity Colleges currently face infrastructural challenges such as inadequate classrooms, obsolete laboratories, poor hostel facilities, insufficient ICT infrastructure, and unstable electricity supply. These infrastructural deficiencies undermine effective curriculum implementation and the integration of sustainable development education.

The increasing demand for quality education and technological advancement has further highlighted the need for infrastructural modernization in Unity Colleges. Sustainable educational development in these institutions requires investment in digital learning facilities, renewable energy systems, environmentally friendly buildings, and modern science laboratories capable of supporting sustainability-oriented education.

Theoretical Framework

Human Capital Theory

This study is anchored on the Human Capital Theory propounded by Theodore Schultz (1961) and further developed by Gary Becker (1964). The theory emphasizes that investment in education, training, infrastructure, and human capacity development enhances productivity, economic growth, and societal development. Human Capital Theory views education as a strategic investment that improves the skills, competencies, and productivity of individuals, thereby contributing to national development.

According to Schultz (1961), educational investment increases the knowledge and capabilities of individuals, making them more productive members of society. Becker (1964) further argued that the quality of educational facilities and learning environments significantly affects the effectiveness of human capital formation. In the context of this study, infrastructural facilities such as classrooms, laboratories, ICT centres, libraries, and electricity supply are essential components of educational investment that support sustainable development education.

The relevance of Human Capital Theory to this study lies in its explanation of how infrastructural investment in Federal Unity Colleges can enhance sustainable development education outcomes. Adequate infrastructure creates an enabling environment for effective teaching and learning, promotes technological innovation, and equips students with sustainability-related competencies necessary for national development. Conversely, poor infrastructure limits students' educational experiences and weakens the development of critical skills required for sustainable societal transformation.

Therefore, Human Capital Theory provides a suitable framework for understanding the relationship between infrastructure and sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have examined the relationship between infrastructure and educational development across different contexts. Owoye and Yara (2011) investigated school facilities and academic achievement in secondary schools in Nigeria using a survey research design. The study found that infrastructural facilities such as libraries, laboratories, and classroom conditions significantly influenced students' academic performance. The researchers concluded that improved educational infrastructure enhances learning effectiveness and institutional productivity.

Ajayi and Yusuf (2009) examined the impact of instructional space planning on students' academic achievement in secondary schools in southwest Nigeria. The study revealed that inadequate infrastructure contributed to poor learning outcomes, overcrowding, and ineffective teaching processes. The authors recommended increased government investment in school infrastructure to improve educational quality.

Fadipe (2025) evaluated stakeholders' perception of infrastructure adequacy for curriculum implementation in Unity Colleges in North Central Nigeria. Using the Davis Process Model, the study found that infrastructural deficiencies in laboratories, classroom facilities, and learning technologies negatively affected science education and sustainable learning outcomes. The study emphasized the need for improved infrastructural funding and maintenance in Federal Unity Colleges.

Hassan, Groot, and Volante (2025) examined the relationship between education funding and student performance in Unity Schools in Nigeria. The findings revealed that increased investment in educational infrastructure positively influenced students' academic achievement and institutional effectiveness. The study concluded that infrastructural development remains a critical determinant of educational quality in Unity Schools.

Ezeudu and Fadeyi (2024) investigated the influence of infrastructure deficits on education and socioeconomic activities in Nigeria. The study reported that poor infrastructural conditions, including inadequate ICT facilities, poor sanitation systems, and unreliable electricity supply, negatively affected educational accessibility and sustainability. The researchers recommended sustainable infrastructural development policies to improve educational outcomes.

Similarly, UNESCO (2023) emphasized the importance of digital infrastructure in promoting sustainable education globally. The report highlighted that ICT facilities and technological innovation enhance knowledge dissemination, creativity, and environmental awareness among learners. However, disparities in access to educational technologies continue to affect developing countries, including Nigeria.

Although previous studies have examined educational infrastructure and academic performance, limited empirical attention has been given to the influence of infrastructure on sustainable development education specifically within Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. Most studies focused on general educational outcomes without adequately examining sustainability-oriented learning. This gap justifies the need for the present study, which seeks to investigate how infrastructural facilities influence sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The descriptive survey design was considered appropriate because it enables the researcher to collect data from a large population and examine the

relationship between infrastructural facilities and sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. The design also provides an opportunity to obtain opinions, perceptions, and experiences of respondents regarding the adequacy and influence of educational infrastructure on teaching and learning outcomes.

Area of the Study

The study was conducted in selected Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. Federal Unity Colleges are federally owned secondary schools established to promote national integration, unity, and educational excellence among students from different ethnic, cultural, and religious backgrounds. The schools are located across the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria and are expected to provide quality educational facilities capable of supporting sustainable development education.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised principals, vice principals, teachers, and senior secondary school students in selected Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. The target population included respondents directly involved in teaching, administration, and learning processes relating to sustainable development education and infrastructural utilization.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was adopted for the study. First, purposive sampling was used to select Federal Unity Colleges based on geographical representation and accessibility. Second, stratified sampling technique was employed to categorize respondents into principals, vice principals, teachers, and students. Finally, simple random sampling technique was used to select respondents from each category.

A sample size of 300 respondents was selected for the study, comprising:

- 10 Principals
- 20 Vice Principals
- 120 Teachers
- 150 Senior Secondary School Students

The sample size was considered adequate for generating reliable and representative findings.

Instrument for Data Collection

Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire titled *Infrastructure and Sustainable Development Education Questionnaire (ISDEQ)*. The questionnaire was divided into two sections.

- Section A contained demographic information of respondents such as gender, age, qualification, and years of experience.
- Section B contained items relating to educational infrastructure and sustainable development education.

The questionnaire items were structured using a five-point Likert scale as follows:

Response Category	Score
Strongly Agree (SA)	5
Agree (A)	4
Undecided (UD)	3
Disagree (D)	2
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1

The instrument measured variables such as classroom adequacy, laboratory facilities, ICT infrastructure, electricity supply, library resources, sanitation facilities, and their influence on sustainable development education.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by experts in Educational Management, Sustainable Development Studies, and Measurement and Evaluation. Their observations, corrections, and recommendations were incorporated into the final version of the questionnaire to ensure clarity, relevance, and adequacy of the research items.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined through a pilot study conducted in a Federal Government College outside the sampled schools. The Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to test the internal consistency of the instrument. A reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained, indicating that the instrument was reliable and suitable for the study.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher administered the questionnaires personally with the assistance of trained research assistants. Permission was obtained from school authorities before data collection. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and assured of confidentiality and anonymity. The completed questionnaires were retrieved immediately after completion to ensure a high response rate.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected for the study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, percentages, mean, and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics involving linear regression analysis and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for the Likert scale was based on a criterion mean of 3.00. Any item with a mean score of 3.00 and above was accepted, while items with mean scores below 3.00 were rejected.

Model Specification

The regression model for the study was specified as:

$$SDE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF + \mu$$

Where:

- *SDE*= Sustainable Development Education
- *INF*= Infrastructure
- β_0 = Constant term
- β_1 = Regression coefficient
- μ = Error term

The model explains the extent to which infrastructure influences sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval and permission were obtained from the relevant school authorities before conducting the study. Respondents participated voluntarily, and confidentiality of information provided was strictly maintained. Participants were also informed that the data collected would be used strictly for academic purposes.

DATA PRESENTATION, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Presentation

A total of 300 questionnaires were distributed to respondents across selected Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. Out of the 300 questionnaires administered, 286 were properly completed and returned, representing a response rate of 95.3%, while 14 questionnaires were either not returned or improperly completed.

Table 1: Questionnaire Distribution and Return Rate

Questionnaire Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Questionnaire Distributed	300	100
Questionnaire Returned	286	95.3
Questionnaire Not Returned	14	4.7
Total	300	100

The high response rate indicated adequate participation of respondents and reliability of the data collected for the study.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender Frequency Percentage (%)

Male	162	56.6
Female	124	43.4
Total	286	100

Table 2 shows that 56.6% of the respondents were male, while 43.4% were female, indicating relatively balanced participation.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Category

Respondent Category Frequency Percentage (%)

Principals	10	3.5
Vice Principals	18	6.3
Teachers	115	40.2
Students	143	50.0
Total	286	100

The table indicates that students constituted the highest proportion of respondents due to their direct involvement in learning activities.

Table 4: Mean Responses on Classroom Infrastructure and Sustainable Development Education

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	Adequate classrooms enhance effective teaching and learning	4.12	0.81	Accepted
2	Conducive classrooms improve students' participation in sustainability education	4.05	0.76	Accepted
3	Overcrowded classrooms negatively affect learning outcomes	4.21	0.72	Accepted
4	Classroom infrastructure promotes students' academic performance	3.98	0.84	Accepted
5	Classroom facilities support environmental awareness and sustainability learning	3.87	0.79	Accepted
Grand Mean		4.05	0.78	Accepted

The grand mean of 4.05 indicates that respondents strongly agreed that classroom infrastructure significantly influences sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges.

Table 5: Mean Responses on ICT Infrastructure and Sustainable Development Education

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	ICT facilities improve access to sustainability knowledge	4.26	0.70	Accepted
2	Internet facilities support environmental education	4.10	0.82	Accepted
3	Smart technologies improve teaching effectiveness	4.18	0.76	Accepted
4	Lack of ICT infrastructure hinders digital learning	4.31	0.69	Accepted
5	ICT enhances innovation and creativity among students	4.14	0.75	Accepted
Grand Mean		4.20	0.74	Accepted

The findings indicate that ICT infrastructure positively influences sustainable development education through enhanced digital learning and innovation.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One

H₀: Infrastructure has no significant influence on sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, linear regression analysis was employed.

Table 6: Regression Analysis of Infrastructure and Sustainable Development Education

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-value	Sig.
Constant	1.214	0.421	2.884	0.005
Infrastructure	0.683	0.074	9.230	0.000

Model Summary Value

R	0.721
R ²	0.520
Adjusted R ²	0.514
F-statistic	85.19
Sig. F	0.000

The regression result revealed that infrastructure has a positive and statistically significant influence on sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria (β = 0.683, p < 0.05). The coefficient of determination (R² = 0.520) implies that 52.0% of the variation in sustainable development education was explained by infrastructure.

Since the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, infrastructure significantly influences sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria.

Estimated Regression Equation

The estimated regression equation derived from the analysis is presented below:

$$SDE = 1.214 + 0.683INF + \mu$$

Where:

- **SDE**= Sustainable Development Education
- **INF**= Infrastructure
- **1.214**= Constant term
- **0.683**= Regression coefficient of infrastructure
- **μ**= Error term

The equation indicates that a one-unit increase in infrastructure provision leads to a 0.683 increase in sustainable development education outcomes in Federal Unity Colleges.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study revealed that infrastructure significantly influences sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. The study established that adequate classrooms, ICT facilities, laboratories, libraries, electricity supply, and conducive learning environments positively contribute to effective teaching and learning of sustainable development concepts.

The regression findings showed a strong positive relationship between infrastructure and sustainable development education, indicating that improved educational facilities enhance students’ learning experiences, environmental awareness, and academic performance. This finding is consistent with the

Human Capital Theory, which emphasizes that investment in educational resources and infrastructure contributes to human capacity development and societal progress.

The findings agree with the study of Owoeye and Yara (2011), who reported that school facilities significantly influence students' academic achievement in Nigerian secondary schools. Similarly, Ajayi and Yusuf (2009) found that instructional space and infrastructural planning improve educational effectiveness and students' learning outcomes.

The result also supports Fadipe (2025), who observed that inadequate infrastructural facilities in Unity Colleges negatively affect curriculum implementation and sustainable educational development. Furthermore, Hassan, Groot, and Volante (2025) established that increased educational investment and infrastructural support improve students' academic performance and institutional productivity in Unity Schools.

The study further revealed that ICT infrastructure significantly enhances sustainable development education through improved digital learning, innovation, and access to global sustainability knowledge. This finding aligns with UNESCO (2023), which emphasized the importance of technological infrastructure in promoting twenty-first-century education and sustainability-oriented learning.

The findings imply that infrastructural development remains a critical factor in achieving quality education and sustainable development goals in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. Therefore, increased government investment in educational infrastructure is necessary for strengthening sustainable development education and improving national educational outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the influence of infrastructure on sustainable development education in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study concluded that educational infrastructure plays a significant role in enhancing sustainable development education and improving the quality of teaching and learning outcomes in Unity Schools. Adequate infrastructure, such as classrooms, libraries, laboratories, ICT facilities, electricity supply, and sanitation systems, creates a conducive learning environment that supports students' academic achievement, innovation, environmental awareness, and sustainability knowledge.

The study also established that inadequate infrastructure negatively affects curriculum implementation, digital learning, students' participation, and the effective delivery of sustainable development education. The regression analysis further confirmed that infrastructure significantly predicts sustainable development education outcomes in Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria. Therefore, infrastructural development remains an indispensable component of quality education and sustainable national development.

The study emphasized that investment in educational infrastructure is not only necessary for improving academic performance but also essential for equipping students with the competencies, values, and technological skills required for sustainable societal transformation in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Federal Government of Nigeria should increase funding for infrastructural development in Federal Unity Colleges to improve the quality of teaching and learning environments.
2. School authorities should provide adequate classrooms, modern laboratories, libraries, and ICT facilities capable of supporting sustainable development education and digital learning.
3. Government and educational stakeholders should ensure regular maintenance and rehabilitation of existing school infrastructure to prevent deterioration and enhance sustainability.
4. Renewable energy facilities such as solar power systems should be introduced in Federal Unity Colleges to improve electricity supply and promote environmental sustainability.
5. Internet connectivity and smart learning technologies should be expanded across Unity Schools to enhance students' access to global sustainability knowledge and technological innovation.

6. Teachers and school administrators should receive regular training on the effective utilization of educational infrastructure and digital technologies for sustainable development education.
7. The Federal Ministry of Education should integrate sustainability-oriented infrastructural policies into the management and development of Federal Unity Colleges in Nigeria.
8. Public-private partnerships should be encouraged to support infrastructural development and technological advancement in Unity Schools across the country.

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